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Impact of Banditry Activities on Enrolment and Curriculum Implementation among Nomadic Primary School Pupils in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was made on comparative analysis between students' enrolment and curriculum implementation on impact of banditry activities among nomadic primary school pupils in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives which were transformed into corresponding research questions and hypotheses. Descriptive survey research method was adopted for the study with a sample size of 463 respondents, this comprised teachers, students and parents. The checklist information obtained from Zamfara State Agency for Nomadic Education was used to answer research question one of the study. While, self-developed questionnaire was adapted to collect information from the respondents. The data obtained from them was used to answer research question two. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research question at the decision rule of 2.5 while Kruskal-Wallis statistical method was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that there is a gradual increase in students' enrolment in nomadic primary schools, and curriculum implementation was not adequate. It has been recommended that the stake-holders of nomadic education should maintain and promote the current enrolment rate, however they should take any possible action to ensure peace and calmness in the state, in order to enable all actors in the curriculum implementation discharge their duties without threat or fear.

Keywords: Nomadic, Banditry, Security Challenge, Curriculum implementation.

Introduction

Education is undoubtedly considered as the most outstanding development priority area in the world today. The core purpose of education is human development. It is belief that education is considered as backbone of development in any society. Prabhat (2021) described education as a process of expediting learning, acquiring knowledge, values and virtue. It contributes to the development of better people around the globe by putting enduring method in which people gain information, skills and ethics. In other words; Wikipedia (2023) described education as a purposeful activity directed at achieving certain aims, such as transmitting knowledge or fostering skills and character traits. With regards to this, Government of all levels establishes schools for formal education from elementary level to tertiary level. As such adequate and organized arrangements were made to ensure that Nigerian children acquire education in an organized conventional school system. Most of these schools especially primary that gives basic education situated permanently at one place or community. However, the pupils that attend the school are predominantly permanent residents of such locality. Despite this effort by the government, it has been observed that a significant number of Nigerian children do not attend the school for at least basic education. This is because they do not have permanent place to live, thus they live considerable part of their life in the bush, using temporary settlements. These people are referred to as nomad they couldn't attend organized conventional school. They include children of migrant fishermen, Fulani-herdsmen, Bororo-herdsmen (Bararaji/Bugaje) and so on. As the government realized that continued reliance on mainstream formal and conventional school system would not adequately serve the educational needs of the Nigerian nomads or the earnest desire of the nation to provide basic education for all its citizens.

Hence, in its quest to regularize this learning gap between children of permanent settlement and their counterpart (nomad), that the Federal Government of Nigeria in 1989 established National Commission for Nomadic Education by defunct Decree 41, now Nomadic Education Act, Cap N20 Law of the Federation of Nigeria 2004, to cater for the educational needs of the socially excluded, educationally disadvantaged and migrant groups in Nigeria (FGN 2005). The commission has progressed and performs several roles in pursuing knowledge to nomads. And it has branch offices in all states and local governments with a view to bring knowledge closer to them, and to ensure smooth coordination, implementation and evaluation of its programmes. Nomads are entitled to education, to enable them contribute their quota in all ramifications of national development. Giving them sound education will no doubt acquaint them with social, economic and political atmosphere around them, so as to understand the kind of contribution they will give in the nation-building. Similarly, giving them formal education will indeed help them to think clearly through which they can understand their strength and weakness. It also helps them to be

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mindful of their nation. Nomadic education is peculiar with teaching of good character such as value, honesty, kindness, equity as well as generosity, courage, freedom and respect to elders. With regards to this, that the National Policy on Education (2022) says; education is the birth right of every Nigerian child and should be brought close to the environment of the child. In other words "everyone has the right to education". Government shall direct its policy towards ensuring that there are equal and adequate educational opportunities for all (Nigerian Constitution 1979). Therefore, educating nomads will help them to differentiate between right and wrong thereby reducing crime rate in the society. It also helps them to maintain rules of law of their immediate environment and making the world a better place to live.

Statement of the Research Problem

Enrolment and retention of students in school cannot be separated; they are like two side of the same coin. Hence, the impartation of sound knowledge at any educational level can be possible if the enrolment and retention of students are adequate. Education system in Zamfara state is faced with some security challenges that appear to cripple the system. Nwannah (2022) reported that between 2019 to date four public secondary schools have been attacked by the revenging bandits and hundreds of students were kidnapped. Nomadic education in Zamfara state is one of the educational categories that undergo through banditry activities in recent times. These banditry activities have impact on the enrolment of students in nomadic primary schools. The available records from Zamfara State Agency for Nomadic Education, have shown that the average enrolment of nomadic students in primary schools before the banditry activities was 1,093 each year. And between 2013 to 2017 when the banditry was at initial stage in the state, the enrolment had reduced to averagely 822 annually. Ismail (2023) posited that although the government has spent millions of Naira in Nomadic Education Programme, the measure of educational attainment among the Fulanis remain low; the quality of education among them is mediocre at best. Subsequently the annual average enrolment of nomads children in primary schools between 2018 to 2023 has risen to 1,819. According to the records the rise of the enrolment within the said years must has relationship with the Ruga-Programme initiated by Government of Zamfara state under the administration of Governor Bello Muhammed Matawalle. This programme was aimed at converging nomads especially Fulanis at one settlement with a view to deprive them from movement from one place to another. It is part of the provision of the programme that the new settlements of Fulanis would be facilitated with all social amenities, such as; veterinary to take care of the health of their animals, dispensary for the health of themselves, schools for their children, skills acquisition centres to learn vocational skills and so on.

Other reasons that led to the rise of enrolment in nomadic schools were incorporation of village heads and Ardos (Fulani Traditional Heads) in the Enrolment Drive Campaign (EDC) for nomadic schools. However, voluntary organization such as "Fulbe Nani Fami" meaning "Fulani have Head and Understood" has contributed a lot in the sensitization and mobilization among the Fulani during the Enrolment Drive Campaign, School Based Management Committee (SBMC) in collaboration with Mothers' Association (MAS) has greatly contributed in rising the enrolment of nomadic schools in Zamfara state. Their effort was being succeeded through inculcation of strong feeling of community ownership and control, with active participation in the overall development of the nomads schools for improved learning outcomes. In relation to this development Ismail (2023) stated that about 85% of the postural Fulanis express their willingness to send their children to school; in some places the Fulanis have even built their own schools through community effort and have asked government to send teachers and teaching materials.

The records made available by the Agency for Nomadic Education Zamfara State Branch revealed that destruction of schools and vandalization of school facilities is one of the hindrances against proper or full implementation of curriculum contents in nomadic schools. Thus, the activities of bandits have put fear in the mind of teachers, which in turn make them abstain from their various working stations resulting in inadequate implementation of curriculum contents to nomads' students. This situation does not affect the activities of teachers alone, but it discourages even the routine school supervision which is done to guide and motivate teachers in order to ensure effective curriculum implementation. It has also been revealed that sometimes the bandits seize the school building and turn it their shelter or hideout. The situation clearly forbids the normal school activities in the affected school. This is in line with the report of Nwannah (2022) saying that, it was no longer news that education sector had totally collapsed in Zamfara state especially when the education calendar has been totally altered due to the insecurity situation. In view of the above the researcher intends to conduct research on comparative analysis between students' enrolment and curriculum implementation on impact of banditry among nomadic primary schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

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Below are the objectives of the study

1. Examine the current enrolment rate of children in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state.
2. Determine the challenges in curriculum implementation in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state.

Research Questions

1. What is the current enrolment rate of children in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state?
2. What are the challenges in curriculum implementation in nomadic primary schools, amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state?

Research Hypotheses

- H₀₁ There is no significant difference in the current enrolment rate in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state.
- H₀₂ There is no significant difference in the curriculum implementation in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study because it involves an investigation covering the entire nomadic primary schools in the state. Dada (2016). Descriptive survey design is the most basic type of enquiry that aims to observe certain phenomena, typically at a single point at a time; and is used to estimate specific parameters in a population. Two objectives were set for the study which were transformed into research questions and hypotheses. The researcher made sample with 463 respondents comprising parents, teachers, and students. The instrument used was self-structured questionnaire which was formed in four-point scale, and had been reviewed by the experts through extensive literature review to ascertain its validity and reliability. Inputs of the experts were used to reverse the instrument. The checklist data obtained from Zamfara State Agency for Nomadic Education was carefully used to answer research question one of the study; and the data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research question two at the decision mean of 2.5, while Kruskal-Wallis statistical tool was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Research question one: What is the current enrolment status of children in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state?

Table 1: Presents Description on the Enrolment of Children in Nomadic Primary School in Zamfara State

Source: Zamfara State Agency for Nomadic Education (2023)

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Table 1 above indicates that the average enrolment of nomadic pupils before the banditry activities was 1,093 each year, and when the banditry began the enrolment rate reduced to averagely 822 annually. The average enrolment of nomads' children between 2018 to 2023 had risen to 1,819. This revealed the enrolment rate has risen grossly in nomadic primary schools of the state. Therefore, null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the current enrolment rate in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities is hereby accepted.

Research Question Two: What are the challenges of curriculum delivery implementation in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state?

Table 2: Presents the Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents' Opinions on the Curriculum implementation in Nomadic Primary Schools amidst Banditry Activities in Zamfara State.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
1.	Teachers have no any fear on their way to attend their school	2.32	.004
2.	You keep your students busy doing lesson in class at all the periods	2.41	0.05
3.	Teachers in your school teach their respective subjects to students fearlessly	2.32	.004
4.	The syllabus of all subjects are adequate delivered in your school	2.33	.003
5.	Volunteer teachers help you to teach your students in your school	2.13	.023
6.	Bandits do not bother nomadic schools in their attacks	2.18	.018
7.	Banditry does not hinder routine supervision to nomadic schools	2.47	0.11
8.	Sometimes bandits seize your schools and turn them their shelter	2.76	0.4
9.	Government relocates some of the nomadic schools to more safer places to encourage you deliver curriculum contents fully	2.33	.003
10.	Nomadic schools in more security challenged places are being closed till further notice.	2.39	0.03
Grand Mean		2.36	

Source: Survey data, 2023

Table 2 above presents the responses of the respondents on the enrolment rate of nomadic children amidst banditry activities in the state. The table shows the grand mean of 2.36 which is lower than the decision mean of 2.5. This result implies that curriculum implementation in nomadic primary schools in Zamfara state is not adequate.

Table 3: Presents the Summary of Kruskal-Wallis Test on the Difference in the Curriculum implementation in Nomadic Primary Schools Amidst Banditry Activities in Zamfara state.

Respondents	Mean	H Calculated	H Critical	df	p-value	Decision
Parents	733.41					
Teachers	682.57	12.06	5.991	2	0.03	Rejected
Students	583.78					
(Hcal=12.06, Hcrit = 5.991)		P=003<0.05			Rejected	

Table 3 shows the result of the test of hypothesis two on the challenges of curriculum implementation. The H-cal of 12.06 while the H-crit is 5.991 at df 2. The P-value is 003 < 0.05 alpha level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the curriculum implementation in nomadic primary schools admits banditry activities is hereby rejected.

Discussion of Findings

From the finding of this study, it was discovered that the enrolment of children in Nomadic Primary Schools has been raised grossly in Zamfara State. This implies that no significant different exist in the enrolment of students in nomadic schools amidst banditry activities in the state. This finding corresponds with the finding of Statista Research and Development (2022) who pointed out that in 2019, there were more than 1.1 million children enrolled in nomadic elementary schools in Nigeria. However, Ahmad (2019) reported that the Chairman SUBEB Gombe State has solicited for the establishment of more nomadic schools to cater for the numerous numbers of nomads' children in school age children in the state, he described the existing ones as grossly inadequate. Akighir and Isa (2013) showed that a small increase in the enrolment rate of children in nomadic schools have not pace with the increase in government expenditure on nomadic education.

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The second finding of this study shows that the curriculum implementation in nomadic schools in Zamfara state is not adequate. This implies that there is significant difference in curriculum implementation in nomadic schools in Zamfara state. The finding is in line with the finding of Taiye (2018) which reveals that the curriculum contents for the children of pastoral nomads is inappropriate. According to him it does not capture practical skills to improve the livelihood of nomads. Rather it focuses on academic achievements that only suit the need of urban children. The finding also highlighted that supervision of officials is inadequate. The finding also indicated that teachers' reluctance to live away from their urban settlement leads to inadequate coverage of syllabus. However, Ogunbiyi and Ojebiyi (2012) whose result reveals that time-frame to many topics and lack of innovative contents effect curriculum coverage in secondary schools in Nigeria. The finding is also in agreement with the finding of Okphanachi (2016) who states that Christian Religions Studies (CRS) curriculum contents are not completely covered in junior secondary schools of Kaduna state.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study it has been concluded that the enrolment of nomadic children in school has significantly raised, this was due to the Ruga-programme initiated by Zamfara state government and incorporation of Ardos, and other relevant agencies such as Fulani Traditional Weeds (FTW) in the Enrolment Drive Campaign (EDC). It was also concluded that curriculum contents are not fully implemented to nomadic schools due to the fear of banditry activities in the state. Thus, teachers and other officials do not attend to school regularly, leading to inadequate curriculum implementation.

Recommendations

1. Education stakeholders especially for nomadic education should intensity their current action in order to maintain and/or extend the enrolment of nomadic children in schools.
2. Government should take any possible action to ensure peace and calmness in the state, in order to enable teachers and supervisors deliver their formal duties freely without fear or tension.

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